

required for d^5 system, suggesting spin-spin coupling between unpaired electrons of neighbouring iron atoms^{10,11}. The bands at 700, 590 and 350 nm observed in the electronic spectrum of Fe^{III} complex could be attributed¹² to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(4G) \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$, ${}^4T_{2g}(4G) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ and ${}^4T_{2g}(4D) \leftarrow {}^6A_{1g}$

Other complexes were found to be diamagnetic as was expected.

Thus, analytical data, high m.p., insolubility in different organic solvents and water, magnetic moment values, ir and electronic spectral data suggest these complexes to be polymeric in nature.

Formation constants of Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes: The dissociation constant of the ligand antimony hydrogen bis(thiolactate) was determined by the differential method¹³ and the value was found to be 3.162×10^{-6} .

Metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting the values \bar{n} vs pL and stepwise formation constants, $\log K_n$, were determined using the following techniques^{14,15}, (i) interpolation of half \bar{n} values, (ii) pointwise calculation method, and (iii) curve-fitting method.

The final values of $\log K_1$, $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ for Al^{III} and Cr^{III} complexes were found to be 3.79, 3.23, 2.86, and 4.05, 3.52, 2.84, respectively.

The formation constants of the other metal ion complexes could not be determined due to immediate precipitation of the complex on titration.

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Preparation and Characterisation of Mixed (Ca+Ba+Cu) Hydroxylapatites

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HYDROXYLAPATITE is assigned the formula $Ca_{10}(PO_4)_6(OH)_2(CaHA)$. In recent years, attention has been directed towards all of the basic calcium phosphates for the elucidation of the processes of calcification in general and for dentistry in particular. Hydroxylapatite is now recognised as the most important of the inorganic constituents of human bone and teeth^{1,2}. It belongs to an isomorphous series of compounds known as apatites. Apatite undergoes a series of cationic and anionic replacement reactions³. $Ca^{2+} \rightarrow Ba^{2+}$ and/or Cu^{2+} replacement reactions in CaHA is of extreme biological significance. They form the basis of incorporation of Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} ions into human skeletal system according to the following equation.

Solid solutions of calcium, barium and copper hydroxylapatites were prepared earlier⁴ by firing mixtures containing various proportions of calcium, barium and copper hydroxylapatites at about 1300°. These samples prepared by the solid state reaction were, however, found to be discontinuous and non-homogenous.

Now an attempt has been made at a new method of preparation of the homogenous solid solutions of mixed (Ca+Ba+Cu) hydroxylapatites over the entire compositional range by the method of coprecipitation⁵⁻⁸.

Stoichiometric quantities of ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Solution A) and a solution containing Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} and Cu^{II} ions in the proportion desired for the solid solutions (Solution B) were prepared separately in CO_2 -free double-distilled water. The pH of the solutions were maintained at ~ 11 . A part of the Solution B was taken in a flask (2l) fitted with two separating funnels and a delivery tube. Solution A and Solution B taken separately in the separating funnels were then added dropwise simultaneously. Precipitation was carried out in CO_2 -free atmosphere and the medium was well stirred by bubbling CO_2 -free air.

TABLE 1—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF $\text{Ca}_{10-(n+m)}\text{Ba}_n\text{Cu}_m(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$ (where $n = 1$)

Sl. no.	Analysis %				Molecular formula	Mol. vol.	g-atom ratio $\frac{\text{Ca}+\text{Ba}+\text{Cu}}{\text{P}}$	Lattice parameter $\frac{\text{Å}}{a \quad c}$	Unit cell vol. $\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} a^2 c$
	Ca	Ba	Cu	P					
1.	39.88	—	—	18.50	$\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	338.32	1.665	9.37 6.86	523.12
2.	29.52	11.10	5.14	16.70	$\text{Ca}_{8.2}\text{Ba}_{0.90}\text{Cu}_{0.90}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	335.25	1.656	9.36 6.85	519.72
3.	25.10	11.43	10.58	16.29	$\text{Ca}_{7.15}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Cu}_{1.90}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	333.20	1.664		
4.	20.64	12.27	15.69	15.83	$\text{Ca}_{6.05}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Cu}_{2.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	324.48	1.662	9.29 6.82	509.74
5.	16.94	11.50	21.01	15.57	$\text{Ca}_{5.05}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Cu}_{3.9}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	329.16	1.658		
6.	13.73	12.88	24.11	15.17	$\text{Ca}_{4.20}\text{Ba}_{1.15}\text{Cu}_{4.65}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	334.06	1.666		
7.	10.10	12.63	28.97	14.87	$\text{Ca}_{3.15}\text{Ba}_{1.15}\text{Cu}_{5.7}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	345.09	1.665	9.16 6.74	489.76
8.	6.64	11.22	34.34	14.67	$\text{Ca}_{2.1}\text{Ba}_{1.05}\text{Cu}_{6.85}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	340.12	1.667		
9.	3.41	11.67	38.23	14.36	$\text{Ca}_{1.1}\text{Ba}_{1.1}\text{Cu}_{7.8}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	345.05	1.666		
10.	—	9.47	44.28	14.24	$\text{Ba}_{0.90}\text{Cu}_{9.1}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	342.14	1.665	8.98 6.62	462.32
11.	—	—	51.27	51.01	$\text{Cu}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$	347.68	1.662	8.83 6.53	440.93

The precipitate and mother liquors were aged under reflux for 30 min to improve the homogeneity and crystallinity of the precipitate. The maintenance of the desired pH during precipitation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate, since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of calcium deficient apatites⁹. The precipitate was washed thoroughly with double-distilled water to free it from ammonium salts and dried at 100°. The samples were analysed complexometrically and their molar volumes were determined by density method using toluene¹⁰ as a solvent.

The X-ray diffraction patterns of the samples were obtained with Siemens powder diffractometer with NaCl (TL) counter employing Cu-K α (Ni-filtered) radiation, (2θ) with a scanning speed of 1° min⁻¹ using tube voltage and current of 30 kV and 24 mA, respectively. The d-spacing and the corresponding a and c parameter values were calculated by the method of Azaroff¹¹ and from these unit cell volumes of the samples were determined (Table 1).

The results of chemical analyses of the samples are given in Table 1. Based on the fact that a mole of each sample has a total 10 g-atom of calcium and/or barium and/or copper, the molecular formula of the samples were calculated from the results of the columns 2-4 and included in column 6 of the Table. The g-atom ratios (Ca+Ba+Cu)/P in a mole of each sample was calculated from the results of columns 2-5 and given in column 8 of Table 1. The fact that the observed value of molar g-atom ratios of Ca/P, Ba/P, Cu/P for the end members and (Ca+Ba+Cu)/P were found to be equal to 1.655 (theoretical 1.67) is consistent with the formation of homogeneous solid solution¹⁰. This was further supported by the closeness of the values of molar volumes of the end members and those of the intermediate samples which lie within the range of end members.

The formation of solid solutions can be further confirmed by X-ray diffraction analysis. It is well established that all the members of the apatite series exhibit hexagonal crystals, belonging to hexagonal-bipyramidal class, 6/m (space group $P6_3/m$)^{12,13}. Lattice parameter showed unit cell dilation and contraction consequent upon the introduction of bigger Ba²⁺ ion (1.35 Å) and smaller Cu²⁺ ion (0.72 Å), respectively in place of Ca²⁺ ion (0.99 Å) in the apatite lattice.

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